

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPECIAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE.

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ANNOTATION

The article discusses technologies for the development of special competencies of future Russian language teachers, modern approaches in the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan; the differences between the competencies and competencies of the teacher are revealed, the formation of the communicative competence of teachers of the Russian language and literature is considered.

Keywords: competence, scientific approach, professional competence, educational system, Russian language and literature.

Modern pedagogical practice requires teachers to be able to teach children how to acquire knowledge and shape the learning activities and thinking of schoolchildren. Therefore, the problems of teacher professional competence, pedagogical skill, creativity, and pedagogical culture are relevant today. The skill and image of a modern teacher is formed through systematic professional work on self-education. The goal of a teacher's personal and professional self-development is success in his teaching activities.

A distinction should be made between teacher competencies and competencies. "The competencies of a teacher are constantly improving and practical abilities, active capabilities, motivational orientation and readiness to carry out creative pedagogical activities with a deep awareness of the social significance of this activity and personal responsibility for the results of one's actions and deeds." Any specialist can be characterized by his professional knowledge, professional skills, work experience, professional potential, and by his personal qualities. I think that all these indicators make up the concept of professional competence.

According to modern scientists in the pedagogical field (Larionova O. G., Verbitsky A. A.), the competencies of a teacher are his rights, duties and responsibilities in the field of pedagogical activity.

One of the key competencies is communication, which ensures successful socialization, adaptation and self-realization of the individual in modern living conditions. Communicative competence means the willingness to set and achieve goals in oral and written communication.

Formation of communicative competence is a long and quite complex process. The main role is given to Russian language lessons. A particular difficulty in teaching the Russian language is the correlation of the subject course and the student's real speech experience, the process of acquiring knowledge about the language and the process of mastering the language. What is the role of the subject "Russian language" in school? What can a teacher of Russian language and literature do to ensure the communicative competence of students?

The subject competencies of a Russian language teacher are convincing for the following reasons:

Help those with academic skills and abilities;

To cultivate an emotional and valuable attitude towards language, to awaken interest in words, to strive to teach how to speak and write correctly in a given language.

Develop the ability to work in the state, interact with other people, and obtain the necessary information.

To develop the communicative competence of students in class and extracurricular activities.

Successful use of this set in teaching means that students know the language, develop communication skills and successfully work outside of school, i.e. in the first world.

The use of information and communication technologies in teaching in English provides students with access to a wide range of modern information in order to develop professional competencies. The use of computer tools and information network sources on the Internet contributes to the development of a high level of information competence, a modern view of technical science, the formation of professional thinking, and increased motivation to study scientific subjects.

The methods used by Russian language teachers are varied:

1. Types of retelling (concise, detailed)
2. Forms of educational dialogue.
3. Reports and messages.
4. Acting as presenters at events.

5. Essays and developments of various forms.
6. Participation in essay competitions.

A Russian language teacher organizes his work in lessons so responsibly in order to use various specialties and skills of students, namely:

1. Fluent work with texts of different styles, understanding of their specifics; necessary skills for text editing and creating your own essays.
2. Conscious fluent reading of texts of various styles and genres, conducting information and semantic analysis of the text;
3. Proficiency in monologue and dialogic speech;
4. Creation of written statements that adequately convey listened and read information with a given degree of condensation (briefly, selectively, completely);
5. Drawing up an outline of the text, theses, notes;
6. Giving examples, selecting arguments, formulating conclusions;
7. The ability to paraphrase a thought (explain “in other words”); selection and use of expressive means of language;
8. Using various sources of information to solve cognitive and communicative problems, including encyclopedias, dictionaries, Internet resources and other databases.

Today, in an innovative environment, a teacher plays different roles: consultant, methodologist, website creator, student’s partner, expert. A competent teacher realizes that the majority of schoolchildren are not familiar with the proposed rules and study them. The teacher’s task is to surround the child with the necessary support that will effectively ensure his socialization and upbringing. A modern, thinking, competent teacher faces many questions. One of the main ones: “Should our education be completely focused on core competencies? And if so, is it possible to leave in it segments of traditional content that represent one or another area of culture and are not clearly pragmatic?”

Only a competent teacher can educate a competent citizen of society. Nowadays there is a lot of talk about the competency-based approach. I would like to hope that this approach will be applied in practice and will not just remain on paper.

To develop literate, connected speech in students in Russian language lessons, the teacher uses lexical and spelling work, grammatical analysis, spelling warm-ups, work with dictionaries and others. In literature lessons, they

are offered literary analysis of a work, memorization of the best examples of fiction, creative written works, and the creation of presentation material.

When studying the Russian language and literature, from the standpoint of developing teacher competencies, students must master:

- information search techniques;
- methods of working with texts of humanitarian content;
- skills in public speaking;
- ways to establish interdisciplinary connections;

Increasing the professional competence of teachers is an urgent problem of the modern educational system, since competence is the sum of knowledge, skills and personal qualities that allow one to perform various actions determined by specific motives and goals set, including by the teacher himself. The pedagogical competence of a teacher of Russian language and literature is formed in the process of activity, improving professional skills, he uses technological approaches in the educational process.

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